

The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Buying Interest in Wardah Lipstick Products (Case Study in Kebomas Sub-district, Gresik)

Trishafira Nuriah¹, Nuruni Ika Kusuma Wardhani²

^{1,2} Management Study Program, Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" East Java, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

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Purpose: Is to analyze the influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on the Purchase Intention of Wardah lipstick products in Kebomas District, Gresik.

Patients and methods: Data has been obtained from the answer of questionnaire testing on 85 respondents who were used as samples in research using techniques purposive sampling.

Results: The results of the study show that product quality has a significant positive impact on consumer buying interest in Wardah Lipstick in Kebomas District, Gresik, brand image has a significant positive impact on buying interest in Wardah Lipstick products in Kebomas District, Gresik.

Conclusion: The better the Product Quality of Wardah Lipstick, the higher the Purchase Intention for Wardah Lipstick products. Similarly, the better the Brand Image of Wardah Lipstick, the higher the Purchase Intention for Wardah Lipstick products.

KEYWORDS:

Product Quality, Brand Image, Purchase Intention

1. INTRODUCTION

The cosmetics industry in Indonesia continues to show promising growth, evidenced by the increasing number of local and international brands that are able to compete in the domestic market. This phenomenon not only affects the industry itself but also changes the way people view their appearance. These changes can be seen from the mindset, needs, and desires of consumers that are growing over time.

For women, cosmetics have become an indispensable necessity to boost self-confidence. In the modern era, beauty is considered a valuable asset that supports their existence in the social environment. Various ways are done to achieve the desired ideal appearance, because women see beauty as an important investment. This condition is a great opportunity for cosmetic manufacturers to compete to present the latest innovations. Increasingly fierce competition encourages companies to continue to innovate and meet consumer expectations (Supriyanto et al., 2021). The right strategy in facing challenges in order to maintain and expand market share is very necessary for companies to use.

Corresponding Author: uruni Ika Kusuma Wardhani

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According to a report by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in 2020, the cosmetics sector recorded an increase of 5.59%. In 2021, this figure is projected to increase to 7%, largely driven by online sales of 25.2%. However, the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 caused a decline in growth to 8%, 13.25% lower than 2019 which grew by 5.25%. By looking at the increasing trend of cosmetics sales, it is estimated that this industry will grow rapidly, supported by beauty trends and new product innovations that continue to emerge (Adisty, 2022).

The variety of cosmetics available today has increased public interest in owning these products. This condition encourages the development of the cosmetics industry in Indonesia, which continues to show a significant increase every year. This trend can be observed in Table 1, which displays the *Top Brand Award* position for the lipstick cosmetics category from 2020 to 2024.

Table 1. Top Brand Index Ranking 2020-2024 Lipstick Category

Brand	TBI (2020)	TBI (2021)	TBI (2022)	TBI (2023)	TBI (2024)
Maybeli ne	6,1%	11,6%	15,8%	19,3%	19,3%
Pixy	5,4%	5,6%	2,8%	3,6%	4,1%
Revlon	8,8%	7,5%	8,5%	6,3%	4,2%
Wardah	33,5%	31,9%	27,2%	26%	22,4%

(Source: Top Brand Awards, 2024)

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Based on the Top Brand Index Table, Wardah occupies the highest position in the lipstick cosmetics category. This advantage is certainly inseparable from various factors that make Wardah still the top choice among the public. However, despite being at the top, Wardah experienced a decrease in percentage from year to year, namely 33.5% in 2020, dropping to 31.9% in 2021, 27.2% in 2022, 26% in 2023, and 22.4% in 2024.

The decline can be caused by several complaints that arise, such as the amount of product content that is considered small, color mismatch between packaging and application results, lack of longevity, sticky texture, and heavy sensation on the lips. Nevertheless, Top Brand Index data shows that Wardah is still able to maintain its dominance in the Indonesian cosmetics market, especially in the lipstick category.

Purchase interest is one of the factors that is very decisive in consumer decisions to buy a product. This psychological aspect encourages individuals to own products by buying them. According to Kotler (2014), various factors that influence buying interest include product quality, brand, packaging, price, product availability, and promotion. Of these factors, product quality has a very important role in attracting consumer attention. Good product quality and in accordance with consumer expectations can increase buying interest and encourage repeat purchases, as explained by Sean Prakarsa (2019), Punarpati and Indarwati (2022), and Fatmalawati and Andriana (2021). However, research by Novitasari (2021) shows that product quality is not always the main factor in purchasing decisions.

Apart from product quality, brand image also plays an important role in shaping consumer buying interest. Tjiptono (2015) defines brand image as the images and beliefs formed in consumers' minds about a brand. This brand image helps consumers judge products, even before they actually know or try them. Bailey and Milligan (2022) also explain that brands can create identity and emotional connections with consumers, which influence their decisions to buy products.

Research shows a positive relationship between brand image and purchase intention. Nugraha (2022) found that brand image has a significant influence on purchase intention, which is also supported by Dewi and Telagawathi (2024), who state that brand image has a positive impact on consumers' desire to buy. However, other studies such as those conducted by Riyadi (2015) and Ikrar (2018) show that brand image does not always have a significant effect on purchase intention, especially in certain groups such as students.

Kebomas Sub-district is one of the areas in Gresik Regency that has a female population of 37,928 people (with an age range of 15-59 years), making it the sub-district with the third highest number of female residents in Gresik Regency (gresikkab.go.id). The potential of the cosmetics

market in this area is growing, especially with the two largest shopping centers that are only found in Kebomas Subdistrict, which makes it the main shopping center for local residents. This condition supports the rapid growth of the cosmetics industry, considering that the majority of consumers in this market are women.

However, the problem faced by Wardah cosmetic products is the decline in public buying interest. This can be seen from a report published by *Compas Dashboard.co.id* in 2024, *Top Brand Awards* data, as well as the results of a pre-survey conducted by researchers among the people of Kebomas District, which shows the following findings:

Table 2. Wardah Lipstick Pre-Questionnaire in Kebomas District, Gresik (2024)

NO.	PERNYATAAN	SETUJU	TIDAK SETUJU
A. Kualitas Produk			
1.	Lipstik merk wardah awet ketika digunakan	11	19
2.	Tekstur matte merk wardah nyaman di bibir	14	16
3.	Aroma pada lipstik merk wardah membuat saya nyaman	15	15
B. Citra Merek			
1.	Wardah adalah merek kosmetik yang terpercaya	25	5
2.	Saya menganggap wardah sebagai merek kosmetik yang modern dan trendi	10	20
3.	Iklan yang di sampaikan wardah sesuai dengan kualitas produk yang di pasarkan	11	19
C. Minat Beli			
1.	Saya memilih lipstik merk wardah guna lipstik yang saya pakai	10	20
2.	Saya lebih memilih lipstik merk wardah dibandingkan dengan Merk lain	9	21
3.	Saya tetap membeli lipstik wardah walaupun banyak pilihan produk lipstik dengan merk lain	12	18

Source: (pre questionnaire results, 2024)

Based on the results of the pre-questionnaire listed in Table 2, most respondents showed an unfavorable view of the Wardah brand in several important dimensions. In terms of purchase intention, the majority of respondents tend not to make Wardah lipstick their first choice. Only about 30-40% of respondents choose Wardah products, while the other 70% prefer other brands. In the aspect of product quality, most respondents also gave unfavorable assessments. As many as 63.3% of respondents felt that Wardah lipstick was not long-lasting, and only 46.7% felt comfortable with its matte texture. The scent of Wardah lipstick was only considered comfortable by half of the respondents. Meanwhile, in the brand image dimension, 66.7% of respondents felt that Wardah did not offer enough lipstick color variations and the packaging design was less attractive. However, around 30-37% of respondents agreed that Wardah's lipstick packaging is quite attractive. These pre-questionnaire findings illustrate a significant gap between consumer expectations and the actual performance of Wardah lipstick products in several aspects. This opens up room for further research related to factors that influence low purchase intention, perception of product quality, and Wardah's brand image in the eyes of consumers.

II. THEORY

Product Quality

One of the things that consumers expect most from manufacturers is superior product quality. Quality itself refers to the overall features and characteristics of a product or service judged by its ability to meet predetermined needs. Marketers play a crucial role in ensuring that high quality is achieved, so that companies can continue to grow and become profitable. Meanwhile, the product itself is all goods or services offered to provide certain value to consumers.

According to Andiani (2017) in Mandasari (2018), products are any type of goods or services provided to fulfill consumer wants and needs. Each product or service has a different meaning for each person, based on the views and perceptions of each consumer. Thus, products are not only judged by their function or usefulness, but also by the emotional and psychological value contained in them. A quality product is one that can provide satisfaction to consumers, both physically and through the experience felt when using it. As stated by Ernawati (2019) in Lola Azizah (2022), product quality plays an important role in influencing purchasing decisions, where the higher the quality of the product, the greater the consumer's interest in buying the product.

Brand Image

Image, according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), refers to the image or perception that people have about individuals, companies, organizations, or products. Meanwhile, the American Marketing Association in Kotler (2005) explains that "a brand is a name, term, symbol, sign, design, or combination of these elements used to identify products or services from an individual or group of sellers and distinguish them from competitors' products". Without a brand, consumers will find it difficult to understand information related to the products offered by the company.

According to Firmansyah (2019: 60), brand image is a perception that forms in the minds of consumers when they remember or consider the brand of a product. This image is formed through experience, knowledge, and information received by consumers about the brand, either through advertisements, recommendations, personal experiences, or other interactions with the product and brand. The brand image that is formed affects how consumers perceive the product and the extent to which they are interested in trying or buying the product. A positive brand image plays an important role in attracting consumers' attention and increasing their interest in finding out more about the products offered. When consumers have a positive view of a brand, they are more likely to seek more information, either through online research, reading reviews, or trying the product directly. This shows that brand image not only influences consumers' purchase intention, but also encourages them to obtain more information about products

that they perceive as quality and suitable for their needs.

Purchase Intention

Interest is one of the psychological aspects that significantly influences a person's behavior, and serves as the main driver that directs individuals in their actions. Schiffman and Kanuk (2019: 7) explain that purchase intention is a psychological element that greatly influences consumer attitudes and actions. External factors such as promotion and price do influence purchase intention, but no less important are internal factors such as perception, emotion, and personal motivation. In this context, purchase intention describes consumers' interest in a particular product or brand, which ultimately influences their decision to make a purchase or not. Consumers' assessment of products is highly dependent on their understanding of the product, especially regarding its functions and benefits. Consumers who have a deeper understanding of the product tend to be more interested and have a strong desire to buy the product. This confirms that the information received by consumers is very instrumental in influencing their buying interest. For example, if consumers know that the product can meet their specific needs or provide benefits that match their preferences, the interest in buying the product will be higher. Conversely, if the information obtained is inconclusive or inadequate, purchase intention may decrease.

Kotler and Keller (2016) state that purchase intention is the initial stage that consumers take before making a purchase decision. Purchase interest is a form of consumer interest in the product that arises after the process of observing and their learning about the product. Consumers who are interested in buying a product show greater attention and desire for the product, which is ultimately realized in real action in the form of a purchase.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Variables in a study are all elements that have certain variations and are determined by the researcher to be analyzed, with the aim of producing information related to these elements and finally drawing conclusions (Sugiyono, 2019). Meanwhile, the operational definition of variables is an explanation of the methods or methods used by researchers to measure a construct so that it can become a variable that can be analyzed. This study uses three variables, namely the independent variable (Product Quality, Brand Image) and the dependent variable (Purchase Intention). The following is an explanation of the three variables:

According to Sugiyono (2019: 126), population refers to a group of objects or subjects that have a certain number and characteristics that have been determined by the researcher to be studied and drawn conclusions. In this study, the population in question is the entire female population in Kebomas Subdistrict, with a total of 37,928 people.

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Sugiyono (2016: 81) explains that a sample is part of a population that is selected based on certain characteristics. In this study, the sample was taken using purposive sampling technique, namely selecting respondents based on predetermined criteria. The criteria used to select respondents are: (1) Consumers who have bought or used Wardah Lipstick products in Kebomas District; (2) Respondents aged 17 to 45 years, because this age is considered mature enough to answer questions appropriately. Given the unknown population size, the sampling technique follows Ghozali's guidelines in Hamiseno (2022), which suggest that the sample size should be between 30 and 100, depending on the number of parameters to be estimated. This study uses 17 indicators and 5 measurement parameters, so the number of samples selected is 17 (indicators) x 5 = 85 respondents.

In data analysis, this research uses component-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method with Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis tool. PLS was chosen because this method is often used in causal-predictive analysis, and is suitable for applications that aim for prediction and theory development. PLS allows researchers to obtain the latent variable values needed for prediction purposes. PLS is a component or variance-based equation model used to relate dependent variables to independent variables in multivariate analysis.

Because the sample used in this study is relatively small (≤ 100), PLS was chosen because it does not require many assumptions and does not require the data to be multivariate normally distributed. Ghozali recommends a sample size between 30 and 100. To test the hypothesis, a probability value with a p-value < 0.05 (5% alpha) is used. If the p-value is smaller than 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted; however, if the p-value is greater than 0.05, the hypothesis is rejected.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Analysis

PLS Model

Figure 2. PLS Model

In the PLS output image above, you can see the factor loading value for each indicator located above the arrow connecting the variables and related indicators. In addition, you can also see the value of the path coefficients located above the arrow line connecting the variables in the model, where the Purchase Intention variable functions as an exogenous variable, while the Product Quality and Brand Image variables act as endogenous variables. This path coefficient indicates the strength and direction of the relationship between each variable analyzed in the structural model.

Validity Test (Outer Model)

Table 3. Factor Loading Value

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X1.1 <- X1	0,570	0,554	0,113	5,033	0,000
X1.2 <- X1	0,628	0,617	0,095	6,630	0,000
X1.3 <- X1	0,457	0,444	0,133	3,441	0,001
X1.4 <- X1	0,683	0,662	0,084	8,141	0,000
X1.5 <- X1	0,697	0,682	0,081	8,582	0,000
X1.6 <- X1	0,640	0,625	0,107	5,987	0,000
X1.7 <- X1	0,591	0,584	0,095	6,206	0,000
X1.8 <- X1	0,595	0,587	0,109	5,461	0,000
X1.9 <- X1	0,558	0,677	0,175	5,471	0,002
X1.10 <- X1	0,507	0,515	0,090	5,647	0,000
X2.1 <- X2	0,618	0,578	0,202	3,063	0,002
X2.2 <- X2	0,910	0,906	0,058	15,710	0,000
X2.3 <- X2	0,522	0,583	0,235	5,794	0,003
Y1 <- Y	0,812	0,811	0,045	18,099	0,000
Y2 <- Y	0,579	0,576	0,116	5,011	0,000
Y3 <- Y	0,660	0,657	0,101	6,534	0,000
Y4 <- Y	0,637	0,632	0,112	5,704	0,000

Source: Data Processed (2024)

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Estimation results in Outer Loading Table show that all indicators have met the good validity standard, with the factor value reaching 50 or more. Since validity test with outer loading has been achieved, this measurement model is ready for further testing the test of the measurement model is done by using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, which describes the extent to which the variance of the indicators can be explained the latent variables. The test with AVE is considered more rigorous than the test composite reliability, with the minimum recommended AVE value being 50.

Table 4. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Product Quality (X1)	0,535
Brand Image (X2)	0,641
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,549

Source: Data Processed, 2024

Based on the test results listed in table 4, the AVE value shows that each construct has sufficient validity to be further analyzed, because all constructs have an AVE value that exceeds 0.50.

Reliability Test

Composite reliability is an indicator that measures the extent to which a measuring instrument can be trusted and provides consistent results. If the tool is used several times to measure the same phenomenon and produces stable results, then the tool is considered reliable. In other words, reliability measures the consistency of measurement results on similar phenomena. The detailed test results can be seen in the following table.

Table 5. Data Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Product Quality (X1)	0,891	0,911
Brand Image (X2)	0,967	0,993
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,907	0,923

Source: Data Processed, 2024

Construct reliability can be assessed through the composite reliability value, where a construct is said to be reliable if its composite reliability value is greater than 0.70, which indicates that the indicator consistently measures the latent variable in question. Based on the test results, the constructs in this study, such as Product Quality, Brand Image, and Purchase Intention, have a composite reliability value of more than 0.70, which means that these constructs can be considered as reliable measuring instruments.

Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

The structural model test aims to measure the relationship between variables, assess significance, and evaluate R-square in the research model. Once a significant relationship between variables is proven, hypotheses relating to customer satisfaction issues can be tested. To test the hypothesis, the bootstrap resampling method is used, with the t statistical test as the main measuring tool (Ghozali, 2008). Assessment of the structural model is done by looking at the R-Square value, which serves to measure the model fit (goodness-of-fit). The R-square value obtained in the relationship between latent variables can be further explained as follows.

Table 6. R-Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,631	0,622

Source: Data Processed, 2024

R^2 value= 0.810 It can be interpreted that the model is able to explain the Brand Image phenomenon / problem by 81%. While the rest (19%) is explained by other variables (other than Product Quality) that have not entered the model and *error*. This means that Brand Image is influenced by Product Quality, and , by 81% while is influenced by variables other than Product Quality, and , R^2 value= 0.666 It can be interpreted that the model is able to explain the phenomenon / problem of Purchase Intention by 66.6%. While the rest (33.5%) is explained by other variables (other than Product Quality and Brand Image) that have not entered the model and *errors*. This means that Purchase Intention is influenced by Product Quality and Brand Image by 66.6% while 33.5% is influenced by variables other than Product Quality and Brand Image.

Results of Inner Weights

Direct Influence

Table 7 Inner Weight

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STD EV)	T Statistics (O/STD EV)	P Values
X1 -> Y	0,369	0,394	0,082	4,503	0,000
X2 -> Y	0,568	0,560	0,094	6,009	0,000

Source: Data Processed, 2024

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From the table above, it can be concluded that the hypothesis:

1. Product Quality has a Significant Positive effect on Purchase Intention with a T Statistics value of 4.503 where the p-values = 0.000 is smaller than the $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) value.
2. Brand Image has a Significant Positive effect on Purchase Intention with a T Statistics value of 6.009 where the p-values = 0.000 is smaller than the $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) value

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Product Quality on Purchase Intention

The results of this study indicate that product quality has a significant positive impact on consumer buying interest in Wardah Lipstick in Kebomas District, Gresik. This shows that the higher the quality of the product offered, the greater the consumer's interest in buying the product. This finding reflects the positive view of consumers towards Wardah Lipstick, especially in terms of product durability, the materials used, and the results felt when using.

One important factor that influences perceptions of product quality is the consistency of standards applied by Wardah. Every batch of Wardah Lipstick that is marketed always goes through a strict quality control process to ensure consistent product quality, regardless of time and place of purchase. This consistency is very important for consumers in Kebomas Subdistrict, because they feel confident that every time they buy Wardah Lipstick, the products they receive will meet their expectations, both in terms of color, texture, durability, and safety for the skin.

This finding is in line with the results of previous studies, such as those conducted by Halim & Iskandar (2019), Tsaniya & Telagawathi (2022), and Astuti et al. (2022), which also show that product quality has a significant effect on consumer purchase intention. In their study, Halim & Iskandar (2019) emphasized that superior product quality is the main factor that drives consumers to make purchases, with consumers more likely to choose products whose quality is guaranteed because they feel more secure and trust the brand. Moreover, good quality not only influences the first purchase decision, but also contributes to increased consumer loyalty in the long run.

On the other hand, Tsaniya & Telagawathi (2022) stated that in the cosmetics and consumer goods industry, product quality is a major consideration for consumers in making purchasing decisions. They found that consumers prioritize quality over price, and maintained and consistent quality has a significant impact on purchasing decisions. Research by Astuti et al. (2022) also reinforces these findings, showing that good product quality can increase consumer satisfaction and have a positive effect on their purchase intention. Consistent quality is also closely related to brand reputation, which in turn affects consumers' decision to make repeat purchases.

The Effect of Brand Image on Purchase Intention

The results of this study indicate that brand image has a significant positive impact on buying interest in Wardah Lipstick products in Kebomas District, Gresik. This finding indicates that the better consumers' perceptions of the Wardah Lipstick brand, the more likely they are to be interested in buying the product. A good brand image includes a positive assessment of Wardah Lipstick as a halal, safe and high quality product. With a strong image, Wardah not only fulfills consumers' needs for cosmetics, but also provides a sense of security and comfort during product use.

One of the main factors that strengthen brand image is how consumers perceive the innovation and variety of products offered by Wardah. Wardah lipsticks are known for their complete selection of colors, consistent quality, and innovations in textures and formulas that suit market tastes. This shows that consumers perceive Wardah as a brand that continues to innovate and always keeps up with the latest trends, which makes this product relevant and reliable. Through consistency in presenting innovative and diverse products, Wardah has managed to maintain a solid brand image in the market, including in Kebomas Sub-district. The wide selection of products offered by Wardah is able to fulfill various consumer tastes, making it the first choice for those who want quality cosmetics and always follow trends. Therefore, an innovative and diverse brand image plays an important role in increasing consumer buying interest and loyalty in the region.

The results of this study are consistent with the findings of Wulandari (2021), Ahmad et al. (2020), and Amala & Budimansyah (2021), all of which show that brand image plays an important role in influencing consumer purchase intention. These studies reveal that consumers' perceptions of quality, value, and trust in brands have a major influence on their purchasing decisions. Consumers tend to choose products from brands with a positive image because they feel more confident and comfortable with the products offered. Wulandari (2021) states that a strong brand image can create positive perceptions which ultimately increase purchase intention. Ahmad et al. (2020) also found that consumers are more interested in products from brands with good reputation and guaranteed quality. In addition, Amala & Budimansyah (2021) emphasized that a positive brand image, which is reflected in product quality and service, has a significant impact on consumer buying interest.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the test results using PLS analysis, to test the influence of several variables on Purchase Interest the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The better the quality of Wardah Lipstick products, the more interest in buying Wardah Lipstick products in Kebomas Gresik District.

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2. The better the Wardah Lipstick Brand Image, the more interest in buying Wardah Lipstick products in Kebomas Gresik District.

Advice

Based on the findings of this study, several suggestions can be made for consideration in decision making, among others:

1. To strengthen the quality of Wardah Lipstick products, in addition to ensuring the product is protected and maintained its quality, it can be considered to increase the attractiveness of the packaging by adding more modern and elegant design elements, which can attract the attention of consumers, especially among the younger generation who are very concerned about packaging aesthetics.
2. Wardah Lipstick could also consider using more eco-friendly packaging materials, such as recycled plastic or biodegradable materials, to support environmental sustainability, which is becoming an increasing concern for many consumers.
3. Further research is strongly recommended to involve other variables that may affect purchase intention, such as price, promotion, and distribution. Research can also be expanded in other regions to find out whether the results of this study can be applied in general or there are significant differences in different regions.

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